

**COVID-19 NING ANKILOZIYA SPONDILITI (AS) KASALLIGI BILAN
OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA UMUMIY STRUKTURAVIY
O'ZGARISHLARGA TA'SIRI: CTX-II BIOMARKERI BO'YICHA
TADQIQOT**

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Koronavirus infeksiyasi 2019-yil dekabrda boshlanib, dunyoning barcha mamlakatlariga tarqaldi. COVID-19 uch yil davomida dunyo bo'ylab 6,6 milliondan ortiq o'lim holatiga sabab bo'ldi. COVID-19 nafaqat bemorlarning sog'lig'iga jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatgan, balki ilgari mavjud bo'lgan somatik kasalliklarining rivojlanishiga ham salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Ayniqsa, ankiloziya spondiliti (AS) kasalligi bilan og'rigan bemorlar COVID-19 ni o'tkazganidan keyin sog'liq holatining yanada og'irlashishini kuzatgan. Ushbu ishning maqsadi AS bemorlarida COVID-19 infeksiyasini o'tkazganlikdan keyin kartilaginal degradatsiya biomarkeri bo'lgan CTX-II ning darajasini o'rganishdir.

Materiallar va Metodlar

2020-2022-yillar davomida Toshkent shahridagi 3- Klinik shifoxona va Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasining ko'p tarmoqli klinikasida 211 nafar AS bilan diagnostika qilingan bemorlar o'rganildi. Ushbu bemorlarning 174 nafari erkak, 37 nafari ayol bo'lib, kasallikning o'rtacha davomiyligi $8,8 \pm 2,4$ yilni tashkil etdi. Nazorat guruhi 40 sog'lom ko'ngillilarni tashkil etdi. Bemorlar ikki guruhga bo'lingan: guruh I (91 nafar bemor) – COVID-19 ni o'tkazgan AS bemorlari, va guruh II (120 nafar bemor) – COVID-19 ni o'tkazmagan AS bemorlari. Guruh I ichida yana ikki kichik guruh mavjud: guruh IA – COVID-19 ni o'tkazgan va asosiy terapiya olmagan bemorlar, guruh IB – COVID-19 ni o'tkazgan va asosiy terapiya olgan bemorlar. Bemorlar to'liq klinik va laboratoriya tahlillaridan o'tkazilib, CTX-II darajasi, rentgen tekshiruvlari va PCR testlari o'tkazildi.

Natijalar

Tadqiqot davomida guruhlarda bemorlarning asosiy shikoyatlari tahlil qilindi. Guruh IA da 88,6% bemorlarda tongda qatishish, 95,1% da orqa og'rig'i, 74,3% da harakat cheklanishi kuzatildi. Guruh IB da bu ko'rsatkichlar mos ravishda 65,1%, 75,2% va 57,3% ni tashkil etdi, guruh II da esa 49,5%, 53,0% va 40,2% ga teng bo'ldi. CTX-II biomarkeri darajasi guruh IA da $2,11 \pm 0,3$ ng/mL ($p < 0,001$), guruh IB da $1,46 \pm 0,14$ ng/mL, guruh II da esa $0,99 \pm 0,18$ ng/mL ni

tashkil etdi. Bu natijalar, COVID-19 ni o'tkazgan AS bemorlarida kartilaginous degradatsiyaning keskin ortganini ko'rsatadi.

Bundan tashqari, bemorlarda kasallikning davomiyligi bilan CTX-II darajasining o'zgarishi o'rganildi. Kasallikning dastlabki yillarida eng yuqori CTX-II darajasi kuzatildi, keyinchalik esa bu daraja pasaygan. Bu holat, kasallikning ilk bosqichlarida umurtqa pog'onasining kartilaginal qismida zararlanma ro'y berishi, keyinchalik esa bonyal to'qimalarning rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq deb hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

COVID-19 ni o'tkazgan AS bemorlarida CTX-II darajasi sezilarli darajada yuqori bo'lib, bu umurtqa pog'onasida kartilaginous to'qimalarning degeneratsiyasini va ankiloziyaning rivojlanishini ko'rsatadi.

COVID-19 ning AS kasalligiga salbiy ta'siri inobatga olinib, bu guruh bemorlarida tashxis va davolash choralarini optimallashtirish tavsiya etiladi.

CTX-II darajalarini o'lchash, AS bemorlarida umurtqa pog'onasidagi jarohatlarni monitoring qilish va prognoz qilish uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari AS kasalligini o'rganishda va bemorlar sog'ligini yaxshilashda yangi diagnostik usullarni ishlab chiqish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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